

Songs of the Sage (4Q510, 4Q511)

Expert source: Joseph Angel, Yeshiva University

Data source: Prayer in the Ancient World

Entered by Brandon Brown, Baylor University

** Expert Source entry, prepared by a Ph.D. RA or DRH Editor from an expert's published work(s), and then personally edited and approved by the expert.*

** Data Source entry, prepared based on data sourced from an external project.*

Entry tags: Late Second Temple Judaism, Abrahamic, Judaism, Early Jewish Literature, Dead Sea Scrolls, Early Rabbinism, Semitic, Hymn, Religious Group, Prayer, Afro-Asiatic, Text, Hebrewic, Ancient Hebrew, West Semitic, Language, Canaanite, Northwest Semitic, Inscription, Jewish Traditions, Biblical Hebrew, Central Semitic, Ritual inscriptions, Ritual Manual, Magic, Ritual text

The Songs of the Sage, a collection of hymns attributed to the Maskil (Hebrew word for instructor or sage – in this case referring to a sectarian Jewish leader of the community at Qumran) for the sake of warding off or protection of the prayerful against evil, is an exemplar of early Jewish apotropaic prayer. The two known witnesses to the composition, 4Q510 and 4Q511, are dated between 30 BCE and 30 CE. Of the two manuscripts, 4Q510 contains only a few legible lines within its fragments, whereas 4Q511 consists of 226 fragments, yielding the majority of the textual material associated with the Songs. The fragments' composition style, language, and format hint that the Songs were used in group study or performance as part of a communal ritual. Though there is no reference to the specific occasion of the ritual's performance, scholars think that the sectarian community at Qumran may have regularly recited apotropaic prayers, of which the Songs of the Sage is a key example. At least three songs are included within the text (though there are indications of several others), and all contain references to the Maskil. At least three of the Songs feature apotropaic incantations or other phrases used to prevent harm from evil spirits and demons. Throughout the texts, praises and thanksgivings are interwoven along with incantations primarily for the sake of praising the Jewish God, with the secondary feature of serving as magic "words of power" that invoke fear in demons and spirits, providing protection from them. In this way, the Songs differ from the contemporary Jewish magical practices involving addresses to the Jewish God and invocation of his name(s) for divine protection. The Songs share some elements of other apotropaic prayer in Second Temple and rabbinic Judaism – protection from Satan/evil, protection from sin and forgiveness for it, sanctification, and the inspiration of God's knowledge and laws to his followers. Yet they stand apart for the ways they reflect the culture of the Qumran community in their dualistic and apocalyptic framework and references to beliefs and practices characteristic of the sect.

Date Range: 30 BCE - 30 CE

Region: Judean Desert (Qumran)

Region tags: Israel, Middle East, Israel, Qumran, Jerusalem, Palestine, Qumran, Judean Desert, Israel in the Second Temple period

Jewish settlement in the land of Israel during the late Second Temple period (Qumran)

Status of Readership:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Sources and Corpora

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Angel, Joseph L. "Songs of the Sage." In *Prayer in the Ancient World*, edited by Daniel K. Falk and Rodney A. Werline. Leiden; Boston: Brill, forthcoming.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: brill.com/display/serial/PAMW?language=en
- Source 1 Description: Angel, Joseph L. "Songs of the Sage." In *Prayer in the Ancient World*, edited by Daniel K. Falk and Rodney A. Werline. Boston/Leiden: Brill, forthcoming.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

General Variables

Materiality

Methods of Composition

– Written

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Inked

– with Ink

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Medium upon which the text is written/incised

– Other textile: Parchment

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Was the material modified before the writing or incising process?

– Physical preparation

Notes: The parchment was made from prepared animal skin.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

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Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Location

Is the text stored in a specific location?

[Note at which point in time, for reference, if known; select all that apply]

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Tomb

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Cemetery

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Temple

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Shrine

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Altar

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Devotional marker

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Cenotaph

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Church

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Mosque

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Synagogue

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Triumphal Arch

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Monument

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Mass Gathering Point

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Cave(s)

– Yes

Notes: Two fragmentary copies of the Songs were found in Cave 4 near the site of Qumran.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Hilltops

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Other natural sanctuaries

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Boundary markers or lines

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Domestic contexts

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Library/archive

– Yes

Notes: Cave 4 contained a large quantity of manuscripts.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Specify

– Specify: The Songs (4Q510 and 4Q511) were found in Cave 4 near the site of Qumran, where the majority of the Dead Sea Scrolls have been found.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Is the location where the text stored accompanied by iconography or images?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Is the area where the text is stored accompanied by an-iconic images?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Production & Intended Audience

Production

Is the production of the text funded by the polity?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Is the text considered official religious scripture?

– Yes

Notes: It appears to have been considered scripture by the community who copied and collected the texts.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Is there a culture of oral recitation?

– Yes

↳ Is there a story associated with the origins of scripture?

– Yes

↳ Revealed by a high god?

– Yes

↳ Revealed by other supernatural being?

– No

↳ Inspired by high god?

– Yes

↳ Inspired by other supernatural being?

– No

↳ Originated from divine or semi-divine human beings?

– No

↳ Originated from non-divine human being?

– Yes

Notes: The Songs are attributed to the Maskil, who was considered divinely inspired.

↳ Are the scriptures alterable?

– Yes

↳ Do the practitioners generally consider the scripture open to alteration?

– Yes

Notes: Based on variants present in the Dead Sea Scrolls, it seems likely that more than one version could be considered authoritative.

↳ Are there formal institutions (i.e. institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders) for interpreting scriptures?

– Yes

↳ Can interpretation also take place outside these institutions?

– No

↳ Interpretation is only allowed by official sanctioned figures?

– Yes

↳ Are there common disagreements? (such as two or more different schools of interpretation?)

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there methods of permanently tabling or resolving debates amongst groups of interpreters?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is there a select group of people trained in transmitting the scriptures?

– Yes

↳ Is the select group of people defined by any specific gender designation?

– Yes

↳ Is the select group of people defined by any age designation?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is the select group of people defined by any form of linguistic designation?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is there a codified canon of scriptures?

– No

Written in distinctly religious/sacred language?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Archaic ritual language?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Considered endogenous by the group itself?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Considered exogenous by the group itself?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Blended languages/creolizations/specific dialects?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Possess its own distinct written language?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ If known: which authority (authorities) describe(s) the language as sacred?

[Select all that apply]

– Other [specify]: The Maskil, an authority of the community, recites the majority of the hymns - employing the religious language of praise, worship, thanksgiving, and admonishment related to the supernatural forces of good and evil mentioned in the text.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Are non-religious institutions involved with the support of teaching religious language(s) for this text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Are non-religious written languages used by the group's adherents to support

religious study of text?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Are oral traditions used to support the religious study of the text?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Intended Audience

What is the estimated number of people considered to be the audience of the text

This should be the total number of people who would serve as the intended audience for the text.

– Total audience: 75

Notes: Estimates of the size of the community at Qumran vary, from several dozen to 150 or more.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Number of audience within the sample region (estimated population, numerical)

– Field doesn't know

Number of audience within the sample region (% of sample region population, numerical)

– Field doesn't know

Nature of audience

[select all that apply]

– Small religious group (actively discouraged-suppressed by larger religious group(s))

Can scholarly and emic notions of the audience differ?

– Field doesn't know

Does the Religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Are there clear reformist movements?

(Reformism, as in not proselytizing to potential new conservative, but "conversion" - or rather, reform - to the "correct interpretation"?)

– Yes

Notes: As a sectarian offshoot of the contemporary Jewish community of the time, the religious group itself represents a reformist movement within Judaism.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Is the text in question employed in ritual practice?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Is it orally recited?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Is there any particular affect of the oral recitation of the text?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Is there any particular affect on the audience of the recitation?

– Yes

Notes: The ritual leads to the blessing of the community's God and a cursing of the evil forces it faces. Taking part in this is part of the group's continuous practice of sanctification, protection from evil forces, and recognition of their sanctification by the God.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Does the affect involve unlocking hidden knowledge?

– Yes

Notes: The Songs presume that the Maskil has already been granted divine knowledge.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ On the reciter?

– Yes

Notes: The Maskil, the who reads and recites the text as he leads the ritual, engages in this practice of sanctification of the religious community and process of blessing and thanking the referenced God and admonishing the evil forces the text addresses.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

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– No

Notes: The Songs presume that the Maskil has already been granted divine knowledge.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Is it read?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Is there any particular affect on the reader of the text?

– Yes

Notes: The Maskil, the reader of the text and leader of the ritual, engages in this practice of sanctification of the religious community and process of blessing and thanking the referenced God and admonishing the evil forces the text addresses.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Does the affect involve unlocking hidden knowledge?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Is there any particular affect on the audience of the recitation?

– Yes

Notes: The audience is protected from evil and demonic forces.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Does the affect involve unlocking hidden knowledge?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Describe the nature of the ritual practice?

– Specify: The ritual is a communally recited apotropaic prayer led by the Qumran community's Maskil, or instructor, and used for apotropaic purposes.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Is the text employed in large scale rituals?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Is the text employed in small scale rituals?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ On average, how many participants are present?

– Number of participants: 75

Notes: Estimates vary from a few dozen to 150 or more.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ How often do the rituals take place?

– Specify: The religious group likely used this and other apotropaic prayers routinely. It may have been part of the covenant ceremony in which recruits to the community swore allegiance to the community's God and denied the world's evil forces (Penner 2014, 190).

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Are there synchronic practices?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: What ritual practices would have accompanied the songs is unclear.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Are there other substances (such as food or drink, for example) that are consumed during rituals?

– No

Notes: Not according to the text.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Is there material significance to the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Context and Content of the Text (Beliefs and Practices)

Context

Is the text itself accompanied by art?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Are there multiple versions of the text?

– Yes

Notes: 4Q510 and 4Q511 appear to be different versions of the text, with the songs in a different order.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Are multiple versions viewed as proper?

– Yes

↳ If multiple versions are proper, is there a differentiation among versions by any means?

– Yes

Notes: The handwriting and size of the two versions differs. It appears that 4Q510 was shorter, and it was also written with smaller lettering, which may indicate a personal use, while 4Q511 is reconstructed to be much larger, and may have been for communal use. The order of the songs also appears to differ in the two versions.

↳ Age of extant version of text?

– Yes

↳ Content of text?

– Yes

↳ Ritual purpose of text?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is there debate about which version is proper?

– No

Notes: Not that is known.

Is the text part of a collection of texts?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Is there a sense of canonization?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Is the text part of a series of volumes?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

If the text is not explicitly scripture, is it part of another important literary tradition?

– Yes

Notes: It is in line with other apotropaic texts of the Second Temple and rabbinic periods.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Cultural with religious implications?

– Yes

↳ Behavioral literature?

– No

Content

Is the text - or does the text include - a ritual list, manual, bibliography, index, or vocabulary?
(Select all that apply)

– Ritual manual

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Are there lineages or a single lineage established by the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Does the text express a formal legal code?

– No

Notes: However, other documents among the Dead Sea Scrolls, such as the Community Rule, do lay out regulations for the community.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Formulating a specifically religious calendar?

– No

Notes: Several passages in the Songs appear to refer to a religious calendar. Other Dead Sea Scroll texts do reveal a religious calendar.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Beliefs

Is a spirit-body distinction present in the text?

– No

Notes: However, the speaker of the Songs refers to the battle between opposing spirits that rages within his body.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Is belief in an afterlife indicated in the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Is belief in reincarnation in this world specified in the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses dicated in the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Does the text indicate if co-sacrifices should be present in burials?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Does the text specify grave goods for burial?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Are formal burials present in the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Are there practices that have funerary associations presented in the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Are supernatural beings present in the text?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ A supreme high-god is present

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic or described in anthropomorphic terms

– Yes

- ↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld)
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god)
 - No
 - Notes: But there is allusive imagery drawn from scripture which refers to the high god as the "king of glory."
- ↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites
 - No
 - Specific to this answer:
Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period
- ↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world
 - Yes
 - ↳ Knowledge is restricted to a particular domain of human affairs
 - No
 - ↳ Knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region
 - No
 - ↳ Knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region
 - Yes

- ↳ Knowledge is unrestrict outside of sample region
 - Yes
- ↳ Can see you everywhere normally visible (in public)
 - Yes
- ↳ Can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home)
 - Yes
- ↳ Can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives)
 - Yes
- ↳ Knows basic character (personal essence)
 - Yes
- ↳ Knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight)
 - Yes
- ↳ Has other knowledge of this world
 - Yes
- ↳ Has deliberate causal efficacy in the world
 - Yes
 - ↳ Can reward
 - Yes
 - ↳ Can punish
 - Yes
- ↳ Indirect causal efficacy in the world
 - Yes
- ↳ Exhibits positive emotion
 - Yes

- ↳ Exhibits negative emotion
 - Yes
- ↳ Possesses Hunger?
 - No
- ↳ Can be hurt?
 - No
- ↳ Can be tricked?
 - No
- ↳ Can be imprisoned?
 - No
- ↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural being other than the high god?
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living
 - Yes
 - ↳ In waking, everyday life
 - Yes
 - ↳ In dreams
 - Yes
 - ↳ In trance possession
 - No
 - ↳ Through divination practices
 - Yes
 - ↳ Only through religious specialists
 - No

↳ Only through monarch

– No

↳ Other form of communication with living

– Yes

Notes: The Maskil has special knowledge of God's will.

↳ Does the text make communication with supreme high-god possible?

– Yes

↳ Can the audience communicate directly to gods through the text?

– Yes

↳ Can the audience communicate through supernatural intermediaries to the high-god, as a result of the text?

– No

↳ Are there notions of inspiration or inspired knowledge?

– Yes

↳ Are there rituals required to attain inspired knowledge?

– Yes

↳ What concepts of inspiration exist? (e.g. clairvoyance, insights, vision of the divine world, awareness of divine omnipresent agency or omnipotence, sigh or vision beyond the five senses).

– Yes

Notes: Awareness of divine omnipresent agency and alignment with divine will.

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

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– Yes

Notes: The community who is responsible for the Dead Sea Scrolls viewed themselves as selected by God as the "Sons of Light."

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Other features of the supreme high god

– Specify: Characterized as supreme source of knowledge which is shared with the Maskil and his community.

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world

– Yes

Notes: The Jewish God here is believed to be omniscient.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Knowledge is restricted to a particular domain of human affairs

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Can see you everywhere normally visible (in public)

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home)

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives)

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Knows basic character (personal essence)

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight)

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Has other knowledge of this world

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Has deliberate causal efficacy in the world

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Can reward

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Can punish

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Indirect causal efficacy in the world

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Exhibits positive emotion

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Exhibits negative emotion

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Possesses Hunger?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Can be hurt?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Can be tricked?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Can be imprisoned?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural being other than the high god?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature
– Specify: Judges the wicked and punishes them. Rewards and protects the righteous.

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living
– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ In waking, everyday life
– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ In dreams
– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ In trance possession
– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Through divination practices
– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Only through religious specialists
– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Only through monarch

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Other form of communication with living

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Does the text make communication with supreme high-god possible?

– Yes

Notes: However, the text is not materially necessary to communicate with the God.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Can the audience communicate directly to gods through the text?

– Yes

↳ Can the audience communicate through supernatural intermediaries to the high-god, as a result of the text?

– No

↳ Are there notions of inspiration or inspired knowledge?

– Yes

↳ Are there rituals required to attain inspired knowledge?

– Yes

Notes: Adherence to the community's regulations is required.

↳ What concepts of inspiration exist? (e.g. clairvoyance, insights, vision of the divine world, awareness of divine omnipresent agency or omnipotence, sigh or vision beyond the five senses).

– Yes

Notes: The Maskil possesses divine knowledge.

Previously human spirits are present

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Non-human supernatural beings are present

– Yes

Notes: The text names an array of demons and evil spirits and also refers to good angels.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Supernatural beings can be seen

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Supernatural beings can be physically felt

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world

– Yes

Notes: These beings are described in very general anthropomorphic terms, but no indication to the level or varieties of their powers is given.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Knowledge is restricted to a particular domain of human affairs

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

- ↳ Knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region
– Yes
Specific to this answer:
Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period
- ↳ Knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region
– Yes
Specific to this answer:
Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period
- ↳ Can see you everywhere normally visible (in public)
– Field doesn't know
Specific to this answer:
Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period
- ↳ Can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home)
– Field doesn't know
Specific to this answer:
Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period
- ↳ Can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives)
– Field doesn't know
Specific to this answer:
Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period
- ↳ Know basic character (personal essence)
– Field doesn't know
Specific to this answer:
Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period
- ↳ Know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight)
– Field doesn't know
Specific to this answer:
Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period
- ↳ Have other knowledge of this world

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Supernatural beings can reward

– Field doesn't know

Notes: They can help or protect humans.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Supernatural beings can punish

– I don't know

Notes: They can harm humans.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Non-human supernatural beings communicate with the living according to the text?

– No

Notes: The texts do not provide information on communication with beings that are not the monotheistic God of the Jewish tradition, but they are referenced within the text as having some influence over - and therefore communicative power with - the religious group. Jewish scriptures attest to non-human supernatural beings interacting with people, however.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion

– Yes

Notes: The Maskil describes the intent of the hymn ritual as "frighten[ing and terrify[ing] all the spirits of the destroying angels and the bastard spirits..."

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature

– Specify: They "lead astray the spirit of (human) understanding."

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Does the text attest to a pantheon of supernatural beings?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Organized hierarchically?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Power of beings is domain specific?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Other organization of pantheon?

– Specify: The text attests to a pantheon of supernatural beings in its references to the monotheistic God as well as his angels and a collection of evil forces (including, but not limited to demons, desert beasts, hyenas, 'bastard' spirits).

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Are mixed human-divine beings present according to the text?

– Yes

Notes: The text refers to "the congregation of bastards" which may allude to the Enochic mythology according to which angels and humans mate and create a mixed race of giants.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Mixed human-divine beings can be seen?

– Yes

↳ Mixed human-divine beings can be felt?

– Yes

↳ Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living according to this text?

– No

Is there a supernatural being that is physically present in the/as a result of the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Are other categories of beings present?

– Other [specify]: Unknown

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Does the text guide divination practices?

– No

Notes: The recitation of the Songs itself creates a protective barrier around the participants.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present in the text?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular

– Yes

↳ Do expectations of ritual offerings play a role in supernatural monitoring?

– No

↳ Supernatural being care about taboos

– Yes

↳ Food

– No

– No

Notes: Food taboos are not referred to in this text but they are present in many of the Dead Sea Scrolls.

↳ Sacred space(s)

– Yes

Notes: The text refers to the heavenly temple.

↳ Sacred object(s)

– Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists

– Yes

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions
 - Field doesn't know
 - Field doesn't know
 - Field doesn't know
 - Field doesn't know

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities
 - Field doesn't know

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about sex
 - No
 - Notes: Sex is not referred to in this particular text, but other Dead Sea Scroll texts suggest that sex is regulated.

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about lying
 - Yes

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths
 - Yes

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness
 - No
 - Notes: Not in this text.

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery
 - No
 - Notes: Not in this text.

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting
 - No
 - Notes: Not in this text.

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk
 - No

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders
 - No

↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes

– No

Notes: Not in this text.

↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene

– No

Notes: Not in this text.

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect the maintenance of the place?

– No

Notes: Not in this text.

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment in the text?

– Yes

Notes: God is asked to punish the evil forces.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known?

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god

– Yes

↳ Done by many supernatural beings

– No

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle

– No

↳ Done by other entities or through other means

– No

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known?

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence?

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce group norms?

– Yes

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness?

– No

↳ Done randomly

– No

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife?

– No

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime?

– Yes

↳ Highly emphasized by the religious group?

– Yes

↳ Consists of bad luck?

– No

Notes: Not in this text.

↳ Political failure?

– No

↳ Defeat in battle?

– No

↳ Crop failure or bad weather?

– No

↳ Disaster on journeys?

– No

↳ Mild sensory displeasure?

– No

– No

↳ Extreme sensory displeasure?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Sickness or illness?

– Yes

↳ Impaired reproduction?

– No

↳ Back luck visited on descendants?

– No

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards in the text?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known?

– Yes

Notes: The reward is the blessing and election of God's chosen group.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Done only by high god

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Done by many supernatural beings

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Done to enforce group norms?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Done randomly

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Highly emphasized?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Consists of good luck?

– No

↳ Consists of political success or power?

– No

↳ Consists of success in battle?

– No

↳ Consists of peace or social stability?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Consists of healthy crops or good weather?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Consists of success on journeys?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Reward in this life consists of mild sensory pleasure?

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Reward in this life consists of extreme sensory pleasure?

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced health?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced reproductive success?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Reward in this life consists of fortune visited on descendants?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Done only by high god

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Done by many supernatural beings

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Done to enforce group norms?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Done randomly

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Highly emphasized?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Consists of good luck?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Consists of political success or power?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Consists of success in battle?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Consists of peace or social stability?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Consists of healthy crops or good weather?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Consists of success on journeys?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Reward in this life consists of mild sensory pleasure?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Reward in this life consists of extreme sensory pleasure?

– No

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced health?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced reproductive success?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Reward in this life consists of fortune visited on descendants?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Other?

– Specify: The blessings asked for of God by the Maskil include protection of the religious group from dangerous non-human or animal forces as well as "vindication by [God's] truth."

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present in the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Is an eschatology present in the text?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Eschaton is in this lifetime

– Yes

↳ At specified time in future

– No

↳ At unspecified time in near future

– Yes

↳ At unspecified time in distant future

– No

↳ At some other time [specify]

– No

↳ Adherents need to perform specific tasks to bring about World's end

– No

- ↳ Divine judgment event
 - Yes
- ↳ Restoration of the world
 - Yes
- ↳ Start of a new temporal cycle
 - Yes
- ↳ Establishment of new political system
 - Yes
- ↳ Establishment of new religious system
 - Yes
- ↳ Will anyone survive the eschaton?
 - Yes
 - ↳ All religious in-group members will survive
 - Yes
 - ↳ A subset of the religion in-group members will survive
 - No
 - ↳ All members of the sample region will survive
 - No
 - ↳ Everyone in the world will survive the eschaton
 - No
 - ↳ Other survival condition [specify]
 - Specify: Adherence to the rules and ideals of the in-group

Norms & Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the text?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the text?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

↳ Honesty/trustworthiness/integrity

– Yes

↳ Courage (in battle)

– No

↳ Courage (generic)

– Yes

↳ Compassion/empathy/kindness/benevolence

– Yes

↳ Mercy/forgiveness/tolerance

– No

↳ Generosity/charity

– Yes

↳ Selflessness/selfless giving

– Yes

↳ Righteousness/moral rectitude

– Yes

↳ Ritual purity/ritual adherence/abstention from sources of impurity

– Yes

↳ Respectfulness/courtesy

– Yes

↳ Familial obedience/filial piety

– No

↳ Fidelity/loyalty

– Yes

↳ Cooperation

– Yes

↳ Independence/creativity/freedom

– No

↳ Moderation/frugality

– Yes

↳ Forbearance/fortitude/patience

– Yes

↳ Diligence/self-discipline/excellence

– Yes

↳ Assertiveness/decisiveness/confidence/initiative

– No

↳ Strength (physical)

– No

↳ Power/status/nobility

– No

↳ Humility/modesty

– Yes

↳ Contentment/serenity/equanimity

– No

↳ Joyfulness/enthusiasm/cheerfulness

– No

↳ Optimism/hope

– Yes

↳ Gratitude/thankfulness

– Yes

↳ Reverence/awe/wonder

– Yes

↳ Faith/belief/trust/devotion

– Yes

↳ Wisdom/understanding

– Yes

↳ Discernment/intelligence

– Yes

↳ Beauty/attractiveness

– No

↳ Cleanliness (physical)/orderliness

– Yes

↳ Other important virtues

– Yes

Notes: Hatred of evil and impurity

Advocacy of Practices

Does the text require celibacy (full sexual abstinence)?

– No

Notes: Other texts among the Dead Sea Scrolls may suggest celibacy was a requirement.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Does the text require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence)?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Does the text require castration?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Does the text require fasting?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Does the text require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods)?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Does the text require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Does the text require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Does the text require sacrifice of adults?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Does the text require sacrifice of children?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Does the text require self-sacrifice (suicide)?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Does the text require sacrifice of property/valuable items?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Does the text require sacrifice of time (e.g. attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.)?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Does the text require physical risk taking?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Does the text require accepting ethical precepts?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Does the text require marginalization by out-group members?

– Yes

Notes: As the members of the religious group are sectarian Jews, they existed on the theological and social margins of the contemporary culture.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Does the text require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household)?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

What is the average interval of time between performances?

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Does the text require participation in large-scale rituals?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present as indicated in the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Does the text employ fictive kinship terminology?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Does the text include elements that are intended to be entertaining?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Does the text specify sacrifices, offerings, and maintenance of a sacred space?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Institutions & Production Environment of Text

Society & Institutions

Society of religious group that produced the text is best characterized as:

– Other

Notes: They are a sectarian Jewish religious group of indeterminate size that probably lived at Qumran.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Are there specific elements of society that have controlled the reproduction of the text?

– A Spiritual Elect

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Are there specific elements of society involved with the destruction of the text?

– Other

Notes: No.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Welfare

Does the text specify institutionalized famine relief?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Does the text specify institutionalized poverty relief?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Does the text specify institutionalized care for elderly & infirm?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Other forms of welfare?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Education

Are there formal educational institutions available for teaching the text?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Are there formal educational institutions specified according to the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Does the text make provisions for non-religious education?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Does the text restrict education to religious professionals?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Does the text restrict education among religious professionals?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Is education gendered according to the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Is education gendered with respect to this text and larger textual tradition?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Does the text specify teaching relationships or ratios? (i.e.: 1:20; 1:1)

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Are there specific relationships to teachers that are advocated by the text?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Are there worldly rewards/benefits to education according to the text specified by the text itself?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Bureaucracy

Is bureaucracy regulated by this text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Public Works

Does the text detail interaction with public works?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Taxation

Does the text specify forms of taxation?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Warfare

Does the text mention warfare?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Does the text dictate how to control an institutionalized military?

– No

Does the text restrict/advocate for participation in exogenous military organizations?

– No

Does the text celebrate/bemoan protection/subjugation by an exogenous military force?

– No

Food Production

Does the text mentioned food production/disbursement?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Bibliography

General References

Reference: Songs of the Sage (4Q510, 4Q511), Tigchelaar, Eibert J. C.. "Evil Spirits in the Dead Sea Scrolls: A Brief Survey and Some Perspectives". In *Dualismus, Dämonologie Und Diabolische Figuren: Religionshistorische Beobachtungen Und Theologische Reflexionen*, edited by J. Frey and E. Popkes, 125–35. Tübingen: Mohr Siebeck, 2018.

Reference: Songs of the Sage (4Q510, 4Q511), Nitzan, Bilhah. *Qumran Prayer and Religious Poetry*. Translated by J. Chipman. *Studies on the Texts of the Desert of Judah*. Leiden: Brill, 1994.

Reference: Songs of the Sage (4Q510, 4Q511), Nitzan, Bilhah. "Hymns from Qumran: 4Q510–511". In *The Dead Sea Scrolls: Forty Years of Research*, edited by D. Dimant and U. Rappaport, 53–63. *Studies on the Texts of the Desert of Judah*. Leiden; Jerusalem: Brill; Magnes Press, the Hebrew University, Yad Izhak Ben-Zvi, 1992.

Reference: Songs of the Sage (4Q510, 4Q511), Newsom, Carol A.. "The Sage in the Literature of Qumran: The Functions of the Maškil". In *The Sage in Israel and the Ancient Near East*, edited by J. C. Gammie and L. G. Perdue, 373–82. Winona Lake: Eisenbrauns, 1990.

Reference: Songs of the Sage (4Q510, 4Q511), Newsom, Carol A.. "Sectually Explicit Literature from Qumran". In *The Hebrew Bible and Its Interpreters*, edited by B. Halpern, W. H. Propp, and D. N. Freedman, 167–87. Winona Lake: Eisenbrauns, 1990.

Reference: Songs of the Sage (4Q510, 4Q511), Newman, Judith H.. *Before the Bible: The Liturgical Body and the Formation of Scriptures in Early Judaism*. New York: Oxford University Press, 2018.

Reference: Songs of the Sage (4Q510, 4Q511), Angel, Joseph L.. "Songs of the Sage". In *Prayer in the Ancient World*, edited by K. Daniel Falk and Rodney A. Werline, Vol. 1. Leiden; Boston: Brill, 2024.

Reference: Songs of the Sage (4Q510, 4Q511), Nebe, Wilhelm G.. "Der Buchstabenname Yod Als Ersatz Des Tetragramms in 4Q511, Fragm. 10, Zeile 12?". *Revue De Qumran* 12, no. 2 (1986): 283–84.

Reference: Songs of the Sage (4Q510, 4Q511), Mizrahi, Noam, and Hector Patmore. "Three Philological Notes on Demonological Terminology in the Songs of the Sage (4Q510 1 4–6)". *Revue De Qumran* 31, no. 2 (2019): 239–50.

Reference: Songs of the Sage (4Q510, 4Q511), Maier, Johann. "Songs of the Sage". *EDSS* 2 (2000): 889–90.

Reference: Songs of the Sage (4Q510, 4Q511), Lange, Armin. "The Essene Position on Divination and Magic". In *Legal Texts and Legal Issues: Proceedings of the Second Meeting of the International Organization for Qumran Studies, Cambridge 1995*, edited by Moshe Bernstein, Florentino García Martínez, and John Kampen, 23:377–433. *Studies on the Texts of the Desert of Judah*. Leiden: Brill, 1997.

Reference: Songs of the Sage (4Q510, 4Q511), Lange, Armin. *Weisheit Und Prädestination: Weisheitliche Urordnung Und Prädestination in Den Textfunden Von Qumran*. Vol. 18. *Studies on the Texts of the Desert of Judah*. Leiden: Brill, 1995.

Reference: Songs of the Sage (4Q510, 4Q511), Krause, Andrew R.. "Spirits of Controversy in My Bodily Structures: Spatiality of Body and Community in Qumran Apotropaic Prayers". In *Dead Sea Scrolls, Revised*

and Repeat: New Methods and Perspectives, edited by Carmen Palmer, Andrew R. Krause, Eileen Schuller, and John Screnock, 52:251-75. Atlanta, GA: SBL Press, 2020.

Reference: Songs of the Sage (4Q510, 4Q511), Krause, Andrew R.. "Protected Sects: The Apotropaic Performance and Function of 4qincantation and 4qsongs of the Maskil and Their Relevance for the Study of the Hodayot". *Journal of Ancient Judaism* 5, no. 1 (2014): 25-39.

Reference: Songs of the Sage (4Q510, 4Q511), Kister, Menahem. "Demons, Theology and Abraham's Covenant (CD 16:4-6 and Related Texts)". In *The Dead Sea Scrolls at Fifty: Proceedings of the 1997 Society of Biblical Literature Qumran Section Meetings*, edited by Robert A. Kugler and Eileen Schuller, 167-84. Atlanta: Scholars Press, 1999.

Reference: Songs of the Sage (4Q510, 4Q511), Hawley, Robert. "On Maškil in the Judean Desert Documents". *Henoch* 28, no. 2 (2006): 43-77.

Reference: Songs of the Sage (4Q510, 4Q511), Flusser, David. "Qumran and Jewish 'apotropaic' Prayers". *Israel Exploration Journal* 16 (1966): 194-205.

Reference: Songs of the Sage (4Q510, 4Q511), Eshel, Esther. "Apotropaic Prayers in the Second Temple Period". In *Liturgical Perspectives: Prayer and Poetry in Light of the Dead Sea Scrolls*, edited by Esther G. Chazon, Ruth Clements, and Avital Pinnick, 48:69-88. *Studies on the Texts of the Desert of Judah*. Leiden: Brill, 2003.

Reference: Songs of the Sage (4Q510, 4Q511), Chazon, Esther. "444. 4qincantation". In *Qumran Cave 4.XX: Poetical and Liturgical Texts, Part 2*, edited by E. Schuller, E. Chazon, T. Elgvin, E. Eshel, D.K. Falk, B. Nitzan, and E. Qimron, 29:367-78. *Discoveries in the Judaean Desert (DJD)*. Oxford: Clarendon Press, 1998.

Reference: Songs of the Sage (4Q510, 4Q511), Bohak, Gideon. *Ancient Jewish Magic: A History*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2008.

Reference: Songs of the Sage (4Q510, 4Q511), Baillet, Maurice. "510. Cantiques Du Sage (premier Exemplaire: Shiraa) and 511. Cantiques Du Sage (second Exemplaire: Shirb)". In *Qumrân Grotte 4.III (4Q482-4Q520)*, 7:215-62. *Discoveries in the Judaean Desert*. Oxford: Clarendon Press, 1982.

Reference: Songs of the Sage (4Q510, 4Q511), Angel, Joseph L.. "A Newly Discovered Interpretation of Isaiah 40:12-13 in the Songs of the Sage". In *Hā-īsh Mōshe: Studies in Scriptural Interpretation in the Dead Sea Scrolls and Related Literature in Honor of Moshe J. Bernstein*, edited by Binyamin Y. Goldstein, Michael Segal, and George J. Brooke, 122:28-39. *Studies on the Texts of the Desert of Judah*. Leiden: Brill, 2018.

Reference: Songs of the Sage (4Q510, 4Q511), Angel, Joseph L.. "Reading the Songs of the Sage in Sequence: Preliminary Observations and Questions". In *Functions of Psalms and Prayers in the Late Second Temple Period*, edited by John Barton, Ronald Hendel, Reinhard G. Kratz, and Markus Witte, 486:185-211. *Beihefte Zur Zeitschrift Für Die Alttestamentliche Wissenschaft*. Berlin: De Gruyter, 2017.

Reference: Songs of the Sage (4Q510, 4Q511), Angel, Joseph L.. "The Material Reconstruction of 4qsongs of the Sage (4Q511)". *Revue De Qumran* 27, no. 1 (2015): 25-82.

Reference: Songs of the Sage (4Q510, 4Q511), Angel, Joseph L.. "Maskil, Community, and Religious Experience in the Songs of the Sage (4Q510-511)". *Dead Sea Discoveries* 19, no. 1 (2012): 1-27.

Reference: Songs of the Sage (4Q510, 4Q511), Alexander, Philip S.. "The Demonology of the Dead Sea Scrolls Edited by P. Flint and J. Vanderkam". In *The Dead Sea Scrolls After Fifty Years: A Comprehensive Assessment*, edited by Peter Flint and James C. VanderKam, 2:331-53. Leiden: Brill, 1999.

Reference: Songs of the Sage (4Q510, 4Q511), Alexander, Philip S.. "wrestling Against Wickedness in High Places: Magic in the Worldview of the Qumran Community." Pages in . Edited by S. Porter and C. Evans.

Jpsup.". In *The Scrolls and the Scriptures: Qumran Fifty Years After*, edited by Stanley E. Porter and Craig A. Evans, 26:318-7. *Journal for the Study of the Pseudepigrapha Supplement Series*. Sheffield: Sheffield Academic Press, 1997.